

Report on Multiplier Event 8 (E8)

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Event: Kodanikuteaduse veebiseminar

Date: 29.05.2024

Target group: Estonian librarians and support staff

Attendance: 60

Objectives of the event:

1. to present the resources collected in different languages
2. to present and illustrate the use of PR6A2 (toolkit)
3. to show all project results on Zenodo

Schedule: 14.00-15.40

1. Mis on kodanikuteadus? LibOCS projekti tutvustus, Svea Kaseorg
2. Kodanikuteaduse e-kursus raamatukoguhoidjatele, Tuuliki Tõiste
3. Kodanikuteaduse tööriistakast raamatukoguhoidjatele, Kaarin Birk
4. 100+ kureeritud kodanikuteaduse alast infomaterjali, Janelle Kirss
5. BESPOC mudel ja tulevikuplaanid, Svea Kaseorg ja Tuuliki Tõiste
6. Küsimused ja kokkuvõtted

Marketing and communication

The invitation with a link to the registration form was sent to our official partners, Tallinna Keskraamatukogu and the National Library of Estonia. The invitation was also distributed via the Estonian Librarians Association mailing list and in TalTech Library's internal mailing list. Introduction and registration link was shared on the LibOCS Facebook page.

Summary and reflections

Multiplier Event #8, milestone #38 of the LibOCS project, took place on 29 May 2024 as a virtual event in MS Teams. It was organised and led by Tallinn University of Technology Library (TalTech) with presenters from TalTech Library and Tartu University Library.

The goal of the event was to introduce citizen science, the outputs and results of the LibOCS project to the Estonian librarians and to disseminate information about libraries' roles and skills for librarians to start with a citizen science project.

Topics covered in the webinar were citizen science, LibOCS project, and the results of (PR6A3), self-paced e-course for librarians (PR3A3), citizen science toolkit (PR6A2), 100+

curated citizen science e-materials (PR6A1), citizen science hub, BESPOC model (PR5A3) and the implementation of the model in UT and TalTech libraries.

After a brief introduction about the purpose of the event, we carried out an engagement activity, asking the participants in a chat poll if they have participated in a citizen science project as volunteers, as citizen scientists, as support for researchers, or as a citizen science project leader. There was also an opportunity to say that “I don’t know too much about citizen science”. As answers of the question showed, citizen science is quite a new topic for a third of the participants. Therefore, we assess that the impact of the webinar was rather great and the event offered new knowledge for Estonian librarians.

The event then proceeded with a presentation about CS and the LibOCS project, followed by an overview of the online course made in PR3 (the course was included in the toolkit). Next, we introduced the toolkit, its location, format, purpose, creation process, sections, and possible use cases. The list of curated resources is included in the toolkit, so we proceeded with showing its layout, purpose, and location in Zenodo. Finally, a short overview of the BESPOC framework was given, with our experience in implementing it in Estonia.

82 librarians registered for the webinar from different library types (public libraries, school libraries, national library, academic libraries) and also some students. On the webinar day, the maximum number of online participants reached was 60.

Feedback from the participants

After the event all registered participants were asked to give feedback on the event via a feedback form. We asked them to rate the usefulness of the webinar on a Likert scale from 1 to 5 and whether there was any new knowledge that they gained, with an additional possibility to leave a free general comment.

We received 18 responses, 15 of them said that the webinar was very useful or rather useful. 3 people rated the usefulness of the webinar with 3. Most of the respondents gained new knowledge, one person said that the webinar was not what was expected.

Materials and recording

Presentations and slides of the webinar were made in Estonian and uploaded in Zenodo under the record [“Kodanikuteaduse kureeritud ressursid, e-kursus ja tööriistakast raamatukoguhoidjatele”](#).

The event was recorded and uploaded to the project’s YouTube channel under [“Citizenship Webinar May 29 2024 - LibOCS Project Results”](#).

Screenshots

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